

Spatial Expansion of Informal Settlements and Socioeconomic Integration in the Northern Part of Kankan (Guinea)

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ABSTRACT

The rapid and unplanned expansion of informal settlements in the cities of the Republic of Guinea poses significant challenges in terms of socioeconomic integration, urban management, and access to basic services. The neighborhoods in the northern part of the city of Kankan, often created outside of urban planning standards, are home to vulnerable populations resulting from population growth and rural migration, but face numerous difficulties. The objective is to analyze the dynamics of expansion and the socioeconomic characteristics in order to propose strategies for sustainable integration into urban policies. To this end, the methodological approach relied on documentary research, geomatics, and a field survey with a sample of 383 respondents.

The results of this study show that the northern neighborhoods of Kankan are experiencing unprecedented spatial growth. According to Landsat images from 2014 and 2024, built-up areas have increased from 34% in 2014 to 78% in 2024 of the total area of the northern part of the city. This spontaneous expansion reveals a strong dependence of the population on the informal sector, with precarious housing conditions and limited access to basic social services. However, these neighborhoods also appear as spaces of resilience and economic dynamism. The study advocates for their gradual integration into Kankan's urban planning through land regularization, infrastructure improvements, and community participation.

KEYWORDS : Integration, Kankan, Spontaneous settlements, Socio-economic, Informal urbanization.

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1- INTRODUCTION

The contemporary world is increasingly shaped by urbanization processes, which are transforming spatial, social, and economic structures on a global scale. However, urbanization should not be interpreted solely as a process of harmonious modernization (G-F. Dumont, 2020, p. 114). In many contexts, it is accompanied by spatial disorder, social inequalities, and precarious living conditions (N. Khiari, 2024, p. 536). This phenomenon is particularly evident in countries of the Global South, where urban growth frequently manifests through the uncontrolled expansion of informal settlements lacking adequate planning and infrastructure (C. Chaline, 1983, p. 714). As emphasized by A.D. Lasserre (1986, p. 198), cities function as key spaces for social and economic integration due to the concentration of populations and activities. Nevertheless, they also constitute spaces of exclusion, segregation, and social fragmentation, particularly when urban growth remains unregulated (Lacour, 2005 ; M. Araba, 2023, p. 2). Informal settlements often described as spontaneous, illegal, or unplanned largely escape institutional planning frameworks (N. Khiari, 2025, p. 82). They simultaneously reflect demographic vitality and the limitations of urban governance systems.

In Africa, this dynamic has reached a significant scale. Urban population rates increased from 31% in 1990 to 54% in 2020, while the number of cities more than doubled. Notably, between 2015 and 2020, urban population growth averaged 6.1% annually, whereas spatial expansion reached 10.1% per year (OCDE/UNECA/BAD, 2022, p. 4 and 14). Such rapid urbanization often leads to the conversion of agricultural land and the proliferation of informal settlements (UNEP, 2014 ; CNULCD, 2017, p. 45).

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Guinea is not exempt from this reality. According to the 2014 General Population and Housing Census (RGPH), the country has 40 urban centers, several of which exceed 100,000 inhabitants, while Kankan, the second-largest city in the country, currently has an estimated population of nearly 250,000 (INS-Guinea, 2017; UN-Habitat & MVAT, 2020, p. 20). This rapid growth generates numerous challenges, including urban sprawl, pressure on public services, unemployment, overcrowding, and the rising incidence of urban poverty (UN-Habitat & MVAT, 2020, p. 50). In Kankan, northward expansion clearly illustrates these transformations, marked by the emergence of informal settlements characterized by precarious housing conditions and limited access to basic social services.

Although these neighborhoods are often perceived as spaces of marginalization and deprivation, they accommodate a significant proportion of the urban population. They reflect a process of unplanned urbanization, driven by massive rural-to-urban migration, weak housing policies, and insufficient urban governance (M. Nourredine, 2011, p. 121). Far from disappearing, these settlements are becoming structurally embedded in urban dynamics and play a crucial role in city economies, particularly through labor supply, the vitality of informal economic activities, and the resilience of their inhabitants (C-B. Saliha, 2024, p. 15). This paradox between exclusion and contribution calls for innovative approaches to their integration into urban planning frameworks (M. Davis, 2006, p. 34 ; M. Araba, 2023, p. 2). The challenge, therefore, is not to deny their existence, but to understand how they can be effectively incorporated into urban planning processes, which constitutes the central interest of this study. Consequently, a key research question emerges: How can informal settlements in northern Kankan be transformed into viable and integrated urban spaces without undermining the socio-economic and community ties that sustain them? The objective of this research is to analyze the dynamics of spatial expansion and the socio-economic characteristics of these neighborhoods in order to propose strategies for their sustainable integration into urban planning.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The city of Kankan is an administrative jurisdiction located in the eastern part of the Republic of Guinea. It serves as the capital of the prefecture and is situated approximately 660 kilometers from Conakry, the national capital. Geographically, Kankan lies between latitudes 10°22' and 10°25' North and longitudes 9°17' and 9°20' West. According to the National Institute of Statistics of Guinea (INS, 2017, pp. 79 and 106), the urban population of Kankan was estimated at 195,002 inhabitants in 2014. By 2023, this figure had increased to 250,607 inhabitants. The present study focuses on the northern part of the city.

The northern area of Kankan comprises the neighborhoods of Bordo, Dar-es-Salam, Missira, Aviation, and Sènkèfara (as of 2022). It is bounded to the north by the Gboutouroun River, near Karifamoriah; to the south by the former airport runway, bordering the city center; to the east by the Milo River, near Balandou; and to the west by the Kissidouougou road, near Gberedou Baranama. The study area covers approximately 29 km² (see figure 1 for illustration).

Map1 : Location of the study area (Northern part of Kankan)

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The study area is located on a vast, gently undulating plateau, featuring a few ارتفاع points such as Sitakourou and Oumarbakourou. The terrain is relatively flat, making it conducive to urban expansion and infrastructure development. The climate is of the Sudano-Guinean type, characterized by a long dry season and a shorter rainy season. Vegetation is predominantly wooded savannah (M.Z. Coulibaly et al., 2025, p. 15). The hydrographic network is mainly composed of the Milo River and its tributaries, including the Gboutouroun, Dèbèkoron, and Kòkoudouni streams. The population is multi-ethnic, largely dominated by the Maninka group, alongside the presence of Fulani and forest-region communities. The main economic activity in the study area is trade, often combined with small-scale livestock farming.

2.2 Methodological Approach

To achieve the objectives of this study, a mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining documentary research, geomatics analysis, and field surveys.

In this context, documentary research involved the review of available sources (such as books, scientific articles, master’s and doctoral theses, reports, and online resources) related to the research problem and/or the study area. This process enabled the collection of secondary data. Geomatics methods were employed to assess changes in land-use and land-cover units between 2004 and 2024, with the aim of evaluating the evolution of informal settlements within the study area.

Regarding field investigations, both qualitative and quantitative methods were utilized. The qualitative approach relied on an in-depth analysis of non-numerical data. An interview guide was designed to structure the discussions and ensure consistency across exchanges. Data were collected using a voice recorder to ensure accurate capture of information. Interviews were conducted with twelve key informants, including representatives from the municipal authority (2), the land administration service (2), neighborhood leaders (5), the National Water Company of Guinea (1), the Electricity Company of Guinea (1), and the Public Works Department (1).

The second method is based on a quantitative data collection instrument (questionnaire), used to gather socio-demographic information and assess housing conditions as well as access to infrastructure. A proportional probability sampling technique was adopted. The sample size was determined using the following formula:

$$TE = \frac{\frac{z^2 * p(1 - p)}{e^2}}{\frac{z^2 * p(1 - p)}{e^2 N}}$$

TE = Sample size

N = Population size (88,113 inhabitants in 2024)

e = Margin of error (5%)

z = Confidence level (1.96 for 95% confidence)

p = Estimated proportion of the population exhibiting the characteristics (0.5)

This estimation resulted in a sample size of 383 households, distributed proportionally according to the population size of the different neighborhoods in the northern part of the city (see Table 1).

Table 1 : List of surveyed neighborhoods in the northern part of Kankan

Serial Number	Surveyed neighborhoods	Sample size	%
1	Aviation	63	63,23
2	Bordo	123	123,18
3	Dar-es-salam	55	55,22
4	Missira	143	142,25
5	Sènkèfara 1	52	51,39
6	Sènkèfara 2	64	64,72
Total		383	100,00 %

Source : M. Kaba et al., field surveys, 2024

Semi-structured interviews were prioritized in this study. The selection of surveyed households was based primarily on the criterion of length of residence, focusing on individuals with a strong familiarity with neighborhood dynamics, particularly those who had lived in the area for more than 15 years.

The processing of quantitative data involved data coding, entry of responses, and the production of tables and graphs, as well as the synthesis of key findings. Data processing was automated using the statistical software SPSS. Subsequently, qualitative data analysis

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began with the transcription of audio recordings, followed by their import into NVivo¹. This facilitated the organization of core themes, the identification of relationships, and the construction of explanatory models.

The final report was prepared using a rigorous interpretative approach aimed at extracting, structuring, and synthesizing the most relevant findings.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the spatio-temporal dynamics of informal settlements and the socio-economic challenges associated with these areas, particularly in terms of living conditions. It also discusses the findings in relation to existing literature.

3.1 Demographic Growth in the Northern Part of Kankan

An analysis of Table 2 indicates that, between 2004 and 2024, the population of the neighborhoods studied in the northern part of Kankan experienced steady growth, increasing from 51,680 inhabitants to more than 88,000, representing an increase of over 36,000 people within two decades. This trend reflects a sustained pace of urbanization, driven by the spatial expansion of existing neighborhoods. Among these, Missira and Bordo record the highest population figures, exceeding 25,000 and 21,000 inhabitants respectively in 2024, highlighting their role as major urban growth poles. Other neighborhoods, such as Aviation and Dar es Salam, also exhibit consistent population increases, while Sènkèfara 1 and 2, although less populated, show proportionally significant growth rates (see Table below).

Table 2 : Population Growth by Neighborhood (2005–2024)

No	Study neighborhoods	2005	2010	2014	2020	2024
1	Aviation	6 520	7 610	8443	10004	11143
2	Bordo	12 740	14 800	16447	19488	21707
3	Dar Es Salam	5 700	6 630	7373	8736	9731
4	Missira	14 700	17 100	18 994	22 506	25 069
5	Senkefara I	5 320	6 190	6 863	8 131	9 057
6	Senkefara II	6 700	7 800	8 642	10 240	11 406
Total		51 680	60 130	66 762	79 106	88 113

Source : INS, 2014 General Population and Housing Census (RGPH), demographic projections, and computed data

In addition to RGPH3 data, the analysis of the collected data highlights a high proportion of polygamously married individuals (65.27%) and an average household size of 14 persons. Regarding the origin of residents, 56% of respondents reported coming from another neighborhood within the city, 31.67% from nearby villages, and 12.33% from other cities in the country.

These trends confirm the dynamics of urban sprawl in the northern part of Kankan, where the demand for housing and services is increasing significantly. They also illustrate the emergence of a polarized urbanization pattern, driven both by densely populated neighborhoods and rapidly expanding peripheral areas.

3.2 Land Use in the Northern Part of Kankan (2004–2024)

At the margins of Kankan’s urban dynamics, the northern part of the city has been gradually reshaped through a combination of informal land practices, demographic pressures, and everyday spatial adjustments. This process reveals a pattern of land use that largely escapes formal planning frameworks while profoundly shaping the future structure of the city.

Table 3 : Land Use Patterns in the Northern Part of Kankan

ID	Land use category	Area (2004)	Area (2024)	Change
97	Built-up area	978	2 274	+ 1 296
101	Bare soil/Savannah	653	418	- 235
102	Gallery forest	75	15	- 60
103	Water/Flood zones	14	2	- 12
105	Forest/Plantation	1 180	191	- 989
Total		2 900 ha	2 900 ha	

¹ NVivo is a qualitative data analysis software developed by Lumivero. It facilitates the organization and systematic analysis of unstructured data, thereby supporting more informed and evidence-based decision-making.

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Source : M. Kaba et al., 2024, satellite image analysis

The analysis of Table 3 reveals a profound transformation of the landscape. The area devoted to built-up land more than doubled, increasing from 978 hectares (34%) to 2,274 hectares (78%), representing a gain of 1,296 hectares. At the same time, natural spaces have significantly declined. Forests and plantations lost nearly 1,000 hectares, while gallery forests decreased by more than 80%. Water bodies and flood-prone areas also experienced a marked reduction.

Although less pronounced, the decline in bare soils and savannah further confirms the increasing pressure exerted by informal urbanization. This uncontrolled expansion of built-up areas reflects the rapid growth of informal settlements, driven by demographic expansion and rural-to-urban migration (see Maps 2 and 3).

Map 2 : Distribution of Informal Settlements in 2004

Map 3 : Distribution of Informal Settlements in 2024

3.3 Evolution of Informal Settlements in the Northern Part of Kankan

According to local tradition, the earliest dwellings of the four original neighborhoods (Timboda, Kabada, Banankododa, and Salamaninda) were established by the four sons of Fodé-Daouda Kaba. The present study area is largely situated within Kabada. As recounted by the belena of Soty Kèmô²:

« The sacrifices made by our ancestors designated the Conakry road as the direction for the expansion of the city of Kankan. The city would grow along this axis. This choice, far from being incidental, reflects both a strategic intention and a forward-looking vision of past generations ».

From this initial impetus, the urban growth of Kankan gradually developed along the Conakry road. The city has benefited from its strategic location near the gold mining areas of Siguiri and along the corridor linking the Guinean forest region to Lower Guinea, thereby attracting new populations and consolidating its role as a regional capital.

Over the past two decades, Kankan has undergone a progressive reconfiguration of its urban fabric, particularly in its northern part. During the 2000s, several neighborhoods (Bordo, Missira, Dar es Salam, Aviation, and Sènkéfara) gradually detached from the parent neighborhood of Kabada, forming a new pole of informal urbanization that now constitutes the structural core of the northern part of the city.

Between 2004 and 2024, the demographic and spatial growth of these neighborhoods accelerated significantly, generating substantial challenges in terms of local governance and urban management. In response, administrative authorities undertook territorial restructuring measures aimed at better regulating urban expansion and improving the provision of basic services. Thus, in accordance with Administrative Decision No. 053/RAKK/P-KK/2024, several subdivisions were implemented in the northern part of Kankan, as illustrated in the table below.

² The terms belena and soty kêmô originate from the Maninka language. The former refers to a spokesperson responsible for conveying messages on behalf of the soty kêmô, while the latter designates the elder or traditional authority of the city.

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Table 4 : Evolution of Informal Neighborhoods (2004–2024)

Neighborhoods in 2004		Neighborhoods in 2024	
Number	Neighborhood names	Number	Neighborhood names
6	Bordo, Aviation, Dar Es Salam, Missira, Senkefara 1, Senkefara 2	19	Bordo Rail, Bordo SOS, Bordo Marché, Bordo ENAE et Bordo Kôkô, Senkefara 1, Senkefara 2, Senkefara 3, Missira Kôro, Sitakourou, Missira Coura et Gbountroun, Missira-mobile, Aviation, Gbountroun, Dar Es Salam, Baladou, Soridou et Dalabani

Source : Prefectural Administration of Kankan, 2024

The neighborhood of Sènkèfara was subdivided into three distinct entities (Sènkèfara 1, 2, and 3). Bordo, due to its rapid expansion, was divided into five neighborhoods (Bordo Rail, Bordo SOS, Bordo Market, Bordo ENAE, and Bordo Kôkô). Similarly, Missira was fragmented into several units, including Missira Kôro, Sitakourou, Missira Coura, Gbountroun, and Missira-Mobile. The cases of Dar es Salam and Aviation illustrate a specific configuration: while the former did not experience significant expansion, a portion of Aviation was annexed to Gbountroun, reflecting the spatial interweaving of neighborhoods and the continuous adjustments imposed by unplanned urbanization. Furthermore, the northern boundary of the city has expanded through the administrative integration of surrounding villages particularly Baladou, Soridou, and Dalabani, which have now been absorbed into the urban dynamics of Kankan.

This territorial recomposition highlights the profound transformations affecting the city, where urban sprawl, combined with often reactive spatial management, continuously reshapes neighborhood boundaries and generates new challenges in terms of urban planning and social cohesion.

3.4 Socioeconomic Characteristics of Informal Settlements

In this study, informal settlements refer to urban areas that develop outside formal regulatory frameworks, within a context of rapid demographic growth and limited urban planning capacity. Their specificity lies in a set of socioeconomic characteristics that reflect both their precarious nature particularly in terms of housing types and their role in the urban integration of disadvantaged populations.

Figure 1 : Distribution of Respondents by Type of Housing Construction

Source : M. Kaba et al., field surveys, 2024

In this study, informal settlements refer to urban areas that develop outside formal regulatory frameworks, within a context of rapid demographic growth and limited urban planning capacity. Their specificity lies in a set of socioeconomic characteristics that reflect both their precarious nature particularly in terms of housing types and their role in the urban integration of disadvantaged populations. The distribution of housing types reveals a clear predominance of semi-permanent dwellings constructed from fired bricks, accounting for 60.59% (232 respondents), followed by permanent structures at 31.59% (121 respondents). Mud-based constructions remain relatively marginal at 6.26% (24 respondents), while highly precarious housing accounts for only 1.56% (6 respondents). This distribution suggests a gradual improvement in residential conditions. As one resident of Missira-Mobile stated:

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« Here in Kankan, most of us use metal sheets to roof our houses. It is cheaper than concrete and easily available in the market. However, during hot periods, the indoor temperature becomes unbearable... yet we have little choice. Personally, I managed to cement the floor of my house because it is cleaner and more durable. But some of my neighbors still have earthen floors, especially in older compounds. Tiled floors are only for those with greater financial means ».

The analysis of housing characteristics highlights practices shaped by economic and cultural considerations, as well as constraints related to the availability of building materials. Regarding roofing, a large majority of households (96.7%) use metal sheets, while only 3% have concrete roofs, and a negligible proportion (0.3%) relies on traditional materials such as thatch. While metal roofing is relatively affordable and durable, it exacerbates thermal discomfort within dwellings. In terms of flooring, 75.99% of households have cement floors, 21% have tiled floors, and 3.01% still rely on earthen floors. These findings indicate that most residents benefit from a minimum level of comfort, although improvements remain necessary, particularly for non-cemented floors that may raise hygiene concerns. Overall, housing conditions are considered “average” by 78% of respondents, suggesting a relatively stable but substandard level of infrastructure. Sanitation conditions remain particularly problematic. The predominant method of wastewater disposal consists of discharging it directly into the streets, as reported by 89% of respondents. Alternative solutions such as septic tanks or drainage channels are used by only a minority. This situation contributes significantly to unsanitary conditions and represents a major public health concern.

Figure 2 : Distribution of Respondents by Occupation

Source : M. Kaba et al., field surveys, 2024

Regarding economic activities and educational levels, the findings highlight both the limited presence of state support and the importance of community-driven survival strategies. The occupational structure shows a strong dominance of informal activities (39.95%), followed by trade (26.63%). Together, these sectors account for nearly two-thirds of the active population, underscoring the central role of the informal economy. Formal employment remains limited, with 14.62% working in the private sector and only 6.79% in the public sector. Agriculture and livestock activities, although traditionally significant, involve only about 10% of respondents, reflecting a gradual shift toward urban-based livelihoods. Retired individuals represent a marginal share (1.83%). These findings indicate that socioeconomic integration in the northern part of Kankan largely relies on survival strategies and self-employment, which are characteristic of urban dynamics in contexts of rapid expansion and limited availability of formal employment opportunities. Indeed, as one resident of Bordo Market stated during our interviews:

« I have been living here in Bordo for more than ten years. I do not have a salaried job. I run a small business selling clothes and shoes at the market, and that is how I support my family. Some of my friends work in private shops, but their salaries are not even sufficient to cover all their expenses. Agriculture and livestock activities still exist, but not as they used to. Here in the city, young people prefer to engage in trade or other small jobs. People often say that Kankan is growing, but formal employment opportunities are not keeping pace. Everyone manages as best they can ».

Income data further confirm the economic vulnerability of households in the northern part of Kankan. More than two-thirds of respondents (67.15%) report a monthly income ranging between 1 and 3 million Guinean francs, reflecting a subsistence economy in which resources barely cover basic needs. Additionally, 19.35% of households live on less than one million francs per month,

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reinforcing the image of a predominantly vulnerable population. Higher-income groups remain marginal: 9.5% earn between 3 and 5 million francs, and only 4% exceed this threshold. This distribution highlights a strong concentration within lower income brackets, revealing not only limited purchasing power but also the predominance of informal and subsistence activities, as already observed in the occupational structure.

Furthermore, the distribution of respondents' educational attainment reveals a high prevalence of illiteracy (46.7%), indicating a persistent educational deficit in informal settlements. In contrast, only 3% have attained higher education, reflecting a very small elite within the studied population. Intermediate educational levels show that nearly one-third of respondents (32%) completed only primary education, while 10.3% reached secondary education (junior or senior high school), and 8% received technical or vocational training. This structure highlights a low level of human capital accumulation, which limits access to formal employment opportunities and contributes to the predominance of informal activities observed in both occupational patterns and income levels. Access to basic social services constitutes a relevant indicator of the degree of integration of peripheral neighborhoods into urban planning dynamics.

Table 5 : Access to Basic Social Services in the Northern Part of Kankan

No.	Level of accessibility	Frequency	%
1	Très accessible	39	10,18
2	Accessible	107	27,94
3	Faible accessible	156	40,73
4	Pas du tout accessible	81	21,15
Total		383	100,00 %

Source : M. Kaba et al., field surveys, 2024

The results reveal limited access to basic social services in the northern part of Kankan. Only 10.18% of respondents consider their access to be very satisfactory, while 27.94% describe it as moderately accessible. In contrast, more than 60% report significant difficulties : 40.73% indicate low accessibility, and 21.15% report having virtually no access at all. This distribution highlights a contrasting yet overall unfavorable situation. It reflects the fragility of public infrastructure in informal settlements and confirms that urban expansion has not been accompanied by adequate provision of social services. As one respondent from Sitakourou stated during the interviews :

« Here in our neighborhood, access to basic services is a major problem. We live almost entirely without public support ; it is mainly private initiatives or individual goodwill that help us cope. To educate my children, I have no choice but to enroll them in a private school because there is no nearby public school. For water, it is the same—we depend entirely on private boreholes since the national water company does not serve our area. When my children fall ill, I am forced to take them to a private clinic or sometimes to the city center, as there is no public health facility here ».

This testimony highlights the severe deficiencies in basic social services in the informal settlements of northern Kankan. The absence of public schools, potable water networks, and health facilities compels residents to rely on private solutions, which are often costly and unevenly accessible. This dependence exacerbates social inequalities, as only households with sufficient financial resources can adequately provide for education and healthcare. The narrative thus reveals a dual reality: on the one hand, the marginalization of these areas within public policies, and on the other, the resulting deterioration of living conditions. It implicitly underscores the need for increased public intervention to improve access to essential infrastructure and reduce socio-spatial disparities within the city.

This perspective is echoed by another resident interviewed in Sènkèfara 3, who stated:

« We do not even have a small local market for our daily needs. Electricity from the national grid is irregular and highly unstable, which forces us to rely on solar panels. Roads exist, but they are so degraded that they become impassable during the rainy season. There is no public lighting, no recreational spaces for children, and no waste management system. All of this makes daily life very difficult and allows insecurity to take hold ».

This second testimony points to an accumulation of infrastructural deficits that directly affect the quality of life of residents in informal settlements. The absence of local markets, unreliable electricity supply, deteriorated road conditions, lack of public lighting, and absence of waste management systems all reflect the marginalization of these areas within urban policies. These deficiencies not only intensify everyday hardships for households but also generate broader consequences, including increased insecurity, environmental degradation, and weakened social cohesion. The findings thus highlight the urgent need for coordinated public interventions aimed at improving living conditions and promoting more equitable urban integration.

3.5 Discussion of Results

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The findings of this study clearly indicate that the rapid expansion of informal neighborhoods in the northern part of Kankan is not an isolated phenomenon, but rather part of a broader dynamic observed in many African cities. Between 2004 and 2024, the population of these neighborhoods increased from 51,680 to over 88,000 inhabitants, highlighting the scale of urban growth driven by rural exodus, natural population growth, and the city's economic attractiveness. This observation aligns with the analyses of Dumont (2020) and the OECD/UNECA/AfDB (2022), which emphasize that demographic growth in Africa is often accompanied by even faster spatial expansion, frequently at the expense of agricultural land and without prior planning.

In Kankan, the extensive growth of neighborhoods such as Missira and Bordo illustrates this "frontline" urbanization, in which built-up areas gradually encroach upon natural and agricultural spaces. This trend, also noted by I. Feindouno (2023) in Kankan's peri-urban areas and by the UN-Habitat Land Report (2017) at the continental level, reflects mounting land pressure that reshapes territorial balances and undermines local ecosystems. Land occupation in the northern part of the city, which increased from 34% to 78% built-up surfaces over twenty years, attests to the intensity of this process and reveals a largely informal mode of urban growth, largely escaping regulatory frameworks.

From a socio-economic perspective, the study highlights the prevalence of precarity and informal employment. More than 39% of the active population report engaging in unstructured activities, and nearly 27% are involved in small-scale trade. These findings corroborate the analyses of Davis (2006) and Chouguiat-Belmalem (2014), who underscore the ambivalent role of informal neighborhoods: on the one hand, they are associated with marginalization and poverty; on the other hand, they serve as dynamic hubs of economic activity and social resilience. In Kankan, residents' testimonies confirm this duality: while incomes remain low and largely oriented toward daily survival, these neighborhoods host networks of mutual support and micro-entrepreneurship that are essential to the local economy.

The observed housing conditions reflect a gradual process of improvement, despite persistent deficits. Most dwellings are constructed with semi-permanent or permanent materials, yet nearly 97% of households rely on corrugated metal roofing, which generates significant thermal discomfort. This situation, also reported by Nouredine (2011) and Araba (2023) in other contexts, illustrates the ambivalence of informal housing: both fragile and consolidating, yet constrained by the absence of adequate public policies. The insufficiency of basic infrastructure (sanitation, electricity, access to potable water) further reinforces the marginalization of these areas and reproduces socio-spatial inequalities, as noted by Khiari (2025) in Tunisia.

Another key finding concerns access to basic social services. Over 60% of households surveyed consider this access to be weak or nonexistent, confirming that urban expansion has not been accompanied by a proportional deployment of collective facilities. This deficit echoes the findings of UN-Habitat (2020), which highlight that informal neighborhoods, far from being temporary, are permanently integrated into urban fabrics without benefiting from institutional support. In Kankan, this situation forces households to rely on private solutions, often costly, exacerbating inequalities between those who can afford such services and those who remain dependent on a degraded environment.

These results underscore the urgency of more proactive regulation. As proposed by M. Araba (2023), the primary challenge in informal neighborhoods is not so much their eradication as their gradual improvement through the provision of collective facilities and integration into urban planning. The avenues discussed in this research (land regularization, enhancement of basic infrastructure, creation of community spaces, and support for local economic projects) align with this perspective. They also echo the recommendations of Durand-Lasserve (1986), who advocated for the recognition of informal neighborhoods as integral components of the city rather than as anomalies to be eliminated.

4. CONCLUSION

This study on the expansion of informal neighborhoods and their socio-economic integration in northern Kankan highlights a complex and contrasting urban dynamic. On one hand, population growth and migratory influx have led to the rapid expansion of the city, manifested in the high densification of peripheral neighborhoods. On the other hand, this expansion has occurred largely within an informal framework, characterized by precarious housing, inadequate basic social services, and persistent marginalization of local populations. The findings indicate that settlement patterns are driven both by economic factors (such as the search for affordable land and proximity to economic activities) and by socio-cultural determinants that reinforce community clustering.

In light of these findings, several recommendations are proposed at different levels:

Urban Planning

- Integrate existing informal neighborhoods into Kankan's master plan rather than considering them temporary;
- Implement a gradual land regularization policy to secure residents and encourage local investment;
- Strengthen coordination among the municipal authorities, decentralized state services, and technical partners to plan coherent and urgent interventions.

Infrastructure and Basic Social Services

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- Prioritize the development of access roads, water supply networks, sanitation, and electricity in informal neighborhoods;
- Develop nearby public spaces (markets, playgrounds, community centers) to foster social cohesion;
- Strengthen the establishment of schools, health centers, and socio-educational facilities in growing peripheral areas.

Socio-Economic Development

- Support income-generating activities and the gradual formalization of the informal economy;
- Establish microcredit programs and provide support for small traders and artisans;
- Valorize community-based support networks by integrating them into development projects.

Institutional and Participatory Governance

- Promote inclusive governance by involving residents of informal neighborhoods in urban planning decisions;
- Create local development committees to serve as intermediaries between the population and authorities;
- Encourage citizen participation in the design, implementation, and monitoring of urban projects.

Research and Foresight

- Extend the analysis to the entire city of Kankan and other Guinean cities to compare urbanization dynamics;
- Examine more deeply the environmental impacts associated with the expansion of informal neighborhoods (deforestation, flooding, waste management);
- Develop urban foresight strategies to anticipate future needs in housing, infrastructure, and services.

However, the study has certain limitations. Although representative, the survey sample was concentrated on a limited number of neighborhoods, which prevents generalizing the findings to the entire urban area. Furthermore, the analysis primarily focused on socio-economic and spatial dimensions, leaving aside other factors such as environmental impacts, local public policies, and institutional dynamics, which merit further investigation.

These limitations open avenues for future research. Expanding the analysis to the entire city, comparing Kankan with other urban centers in Guinea and West Africa, and incorporating environmental and climate-related concerns linked to informal urbanization would be valuable. A participatory approach involving residents, local authorities, and development partners could also refine integration strategies and ensure their sustainability.

In sum, the urban future of Kankan will depend on its ability to transform informal neighborhoods into levers of inclusion and development. The integration of these areas into urban planning should not be seen as a constraint but as an opportunity to build a more balanced, equitable, and resilient city.

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